
IMPACT OF ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORTS AND ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE ON EMPLOYED JOB SATISFACTION OF THE ACADEMICS STAFF OF KANO STATE POLYTECHNIC

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Abstract

Job satisfaction has a significant role in the productivity of employees, which ultimately plays a crucial role in the progress of an organization. Employees were more satisfied when they felt they are rewarded for their work they do and the rewards are according to their contribution to the organization. This research was aimed to examine the effect of organizational supports (organizational reward and job condition) and organizational justice (procedural justice, distributive justice, interpersonal justice and information justice) on job satisfaction. The target populations under this study are the five hundred and ninety-five (595) academic staff of Kano state polytechnic. Sample of two hundred and thirty-four (234) respondents were selected from the academic staff of Kano state polytechnic using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size. The study employed stratified random sampling techniques, which means choosing from five units' schools which constitutes a stratum. The principal instrument to be used for the purpose of this study is questionnaire, which was designed using a 5-point Likert scale. Multiple regression analysis was employed to test the hypothesized model of the study. The result of regression analysis shows that procedural justice has significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction of the academic staff of Kano State Polytechnic. The result also confirmed that distributive justice has significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction of the academic staffs of Kano State Polytechnic. The result of the multiple regression analysis shows insignificant negative effect between informational justice and employee job satisfaction of Kano State Polytechnic. The result shows that interpersonal justice has significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction of the academic staff of Kano State Polytechnic. Finally, this study revealed that organizational reward and job condition have significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction of Kano State Polytechnic. Recommendation which can depict with ease the trend in production, adopting reinforcement techniques that reward workers who excel; encouraging feedback when faced with new projects.

KEY WORDS: Organizational, supports, job satisfaction, academics staff, Kano State Polytechnic.

1.1 Introduction

Job satisfaction and work performance of the employees within an organization is becoming vital concern for the organizational management and thus to achieve goals and objectives (Schmidt, 2013; Denizer, 2008; Bakare, 2012). In recent times, due to changes in organizational management approaches such as changes in organizational structures and cultures because of competitiveness in the market in which they are operating its business, leading to focus on the job satisfaction and performance of the employees within the organization (Jones, Latreille & Sloane, 2008).

Job satisfaction of employees plays a very vital role on the performance of an organization. It is essential to know as to how employees can be retained through making them satisfied and motivated to achieve extraordinary results. Target and achievement depend on employee satisfaction and in turn contribute for organizational success and growth, enhances the productivity, and increases the quality of work (Christina & Chi, 2009; Latif et al, 2013).

It is indispensable for an organization to exactly feel as to what employees feel, think, and to discover and make strategies that how the staff dedication and commitment can be improved. Through this initiative business outcomes can be improved, productivity can be enhanced, commitment can get strengthened. Increasing staff satisfaction is very vital and important factor for the success of an organization (Kivimaki, and Kalimo, 2013). Job satisfaction is quite highly correlated with overall happiness of the employees within an organization and can be looked at as one of the main components for the work performance of those employees (Akafo. and Boateng. 2015).

As an employee receives instructions from management and reacts to such decisions as being fair or unfair, is very important because it can influence the employees' subsequent behaviour (e.g. intention to resign, job satisfaction, job commitment and engagement) that can have a huge impact on the success of carrying out the task's assignment to them. In essence, the perception of fairness is very important in an organization; how employees perceive Justice would greatly affect organizational performance and success by creating greater trust between employer and employees, improving teamwork increasing the level of employee's citizenship behaviour and employees (Fernandes, & Awamleh, 2010).

Employees were more satisfied when they felt they were fairly rewarded fairly for the work they have made and these rewards are according to their contributions for organization and in harmony with reward policies of organization (Al-zubi, 2012). Job satisfaction has a significant role in the productivity of employees ultimately, which plays a crucial role in the progress of an organization. As now world is like global village so employ can move not only within country but they can move to other countries as well.

Due to high competition organizations are always in search of qualified employees and human resources is such types of assets which is most difficult to retain so organization should give concentration to those factors that can affects satisfaction of employees. In these factors organization justice has key importance which explained how the individual perceives about the fairness of rewards he should get and what actually he received from the organization (Fernandes & Awamleh, 2010). Highly satisfied employee perceived that their organization would take care of the quality work to the organization and to perform more productivity (Fatt, et al., 2010).

1.2 Statement of the Problem/Justification

When employees react to the way they are treated at work, their motivation to respond cannot be understood adequately without taking in to account two separate nations of fairness

distribution justice and procedural justice (Folger & Konovsky, 1989, Greenberg, 1987). Adams (1963) conceptualized fairness by stating that employees determine whether they have been treated fairly at work by comparing their own pay-off ratio of outcomes (such as pay or status) to inputs (such as effort or time) to the ratio their co-workers. This is called distributive justice, and it presents employees' perceptions about the fairness of managerial decision relative to the distribution of outcomes such as pay, promotion, etc. If employees perceive that the decision is fair, they are less likely to form an intention to quit and distributive justice perceptions are associated with pay raise satisfactions (Folger R. & Konovsky, 1989).

1.3 Objective(s) of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of organizational supports, organizational justices on employee job satisfaction of the academic staff of Kano State Polytechnic. The specific objectives of the study are;

- i. To determine the impact of procedural justice on employee job satisfaction of the academic staff of Kano State Polytechnic.
- ii. To examine the impact of distribution justice on employee job satisfaction of the academic staff of Kano State Polytechnic.
- iii. To investigate the impact of interpersonal justice on employee job satisfaction of the academic staff of Kano State Polytechnic.
- iv. To establish the impact of informational justice on employee job satisfaction of the academic staff of Kano State Polytechnic.

1.4 Research Questions

- i. What is the impact between procedural justice and employee job satisfaction of the academic staff of Kano State Polytechnic?
- ii. How does the impact of distribution justice on employee job satisfaction of the academic staff of Kano State Polytechnic.?
- iii. Is there any informational justice and employee job satisfaction of the academic staff of Kano State Polytechnic.?

1.5 Conceptual Framework

Concept of Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction has been widely studied over the four decades of organizational research. Job satisfaction has been defined and measured both as a global concept with multiple dimension or facts (Luthans, 2002). In general, overall job satisfaction has been defined as a function of the perceived relationship between what one wants from one's job and what one perceived it as offering "(Locke, 1969). Job Satisfaction is critical to retaining and attracting well-qualified personal. Job satisfaction is an attitude that people have about their jobs and the organizations in which they perform these jobs. Methodologically, we can define job satisfaction as an employee's affective reaction to a job, based on a comparison between actual outcomes and designed outcomes (Mosadeghad, 2003). Job satisfaction is generally recognized as a multifaceted construct that includes employee feelings about a variety of both intrinsic job elements

Furthermore, more satisfied employees have more innovative activities continuous quality improvement and participation in decision making in organization (Kivimaki & Kalimo, 1994). Job satisfaction is also found to be positively-related to customer's satisfaction (Rad & Yarmohammadian, 2006).

Job satisfaction has been defined as connection between what one expects from job and what his perception about getting from job (Locke, 1976). Job satisfaction has been extensively studied by researchers from last four decades. Job satisfaction is taken seriously based on assumption that higher job satisfaction led to higher work performance (Yang, Brown, & Byongook, 2011).

Concepts of Organizational Support

Organizational Support get high consideration since perceived organizational support as sensitivity and opinion of employee regarding the degree to which their involvement is appreciated and recognized by their institution and cares about their well-being. According to Wann-yih and Lawrence (2011) perceived organizational support is an employee's point of view regarding the extent to which organization is concerned for their welfare and consider its effort for organization. They put more efforts when there is an indication that all efforts will be owned and will be rewarded by organization. Wahab, & Nowak (2009) found that the job attitude and behavior of employees is highly affected by different institutional policies organizational outcomes. It is the belief of employees that the organization considers their effort in accomplishment of organizational goals.

Therefore, employees always engage themselves in activities which keep them close and respected to their employer. Ghani (2006) stated that employ that employees lead to organizational success. According to Colakoglu, et al. (2010) organizational support is of great importance for employees and considered by employees as key factor which also enhance the job satisfaction and the organizational commitment of employees throughout (Huo et al., 1996).

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study was drawn from a broad research tradition which links interpersonal working relationships, attitudes such as job satisfaction in relationship to employee's justice perceptions and organizational support. The theory that will guide this study are the Maslow's Theory of Motivation/Satisfaction and Herzberg Two Factor Theory.

Maslow's Theory of Motivation/Satisfaction (1943)

Maslow's hierarchy of needs is "the most widely mentioned theory of motivation and satisfaction" (Wehrich & Koontz, 1999), Building on humanistic psychology and the clinical experiences, Abraham Maslow argued that an individual's motivational requirements could be ordered as a hierarchy. Once a given level of needs is satisfied, it no longer helps to motivate. Thus, next higher level of need has to be activated in order to motivate and thereby satisfy the individual (Luthans, 2005:240). Maslow (1943) identified five levels of need hierarchy:

1. Physical needs: (food, clothing, shelter, sex),
 2. Safety needs: (physical protection),
 3. Social: (develop close associations with others),
 4. Esteem/Achievement needs: (prestige given by others), and
 5. Self-Actualization: (self-fulfillment and accomplishment through personal growth)
- (Maslow, 1970).

Herzberg Two Factor Theory

Herzberg's Two-Factor theory was used as a framework for this study. Herzberg's two-factor theory is concerned with factors that are responsible for job satisfaction and Job dissatisfaction. His two-factor theory was derived from Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs. He conducted a widely reported motivational study following Maslow's model using

203 Accountants and Engineers employed by firms in and around Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, USA which he tagged what do people want from their jobs? Herzberg (1967) argued that an individual's relation to his work is a basic one and that his attitude to his work can determine his success or failure.

Subjects were asked to relate times when they felt exceptionally good or exceptionally bad with their present job or any previous job. Responses to the interviews were generally consistent and revealed that there were two different sets of factors affecting motivation and work. This led to the two-factor theory of motivation and job satisfaction. He categorized the responses and reported.

1.6 Methodology

The primary objective of this study is investigating the organizational justice and organizational support on employee job satisfaction of academic Staff Kano State Polytechnic. The main purpose of this chapter is to show the approaches used in carrying out this research and to demonstrate how the approached are delivered to meet the set objectives of the research. This section explains the research design and other methodological issues that are involved in this study. The population of the study is defined, as well as the sampling technique and the sample size of the study. The dependent and the independent variables are also identified, and their measurement explained. The methods of data collection, the techniques of data analysis and the model of the specification are explained. Lastly, validity and reliability of the instrument was also explained.

1.7 Result and Discussion

Table 7.1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
School Units		
School of Management Studies	79	37.7
School of Technology	70	33.4
School of Environmental Studies Gwarzo	20	9.57
School of Rural Development Studies, Rano	20	9.57
School of General Studies	20	9.57
Total	209	100
Gender		
Male	166	79.0
Female	43	21.0
Total	209	100.0
Age		
21-30 years	40	19.3
31-40 years	75	35.8
41-50 years	59	28.2
51 year and above	35	16.7
Total	209	100.0
Marital Status		
Married	157	75.1
Single	48	22.9
Widowed	2	0.95
Divorced or separated	2	0.95
Total	209	100.0
Educational qualifications		
Bachelor degree (BSc, B.A, B.Ed.,HND)	92	44.0

Masters of Science (MSc, M. A, M.Ed.)	110	52.6
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)	7	3.4
Total	209	100.0
Service length		
Less than 1 year	15	7.17
1-5 years	55	26.3
6-10 years	101	48.3
11 years and above	38	18.3
Total	209	100.0

Source: Field Survey (2025)

As shown in table 7.1 the highest number of respondents is chosen from the school of management studies with the total number of 79 (37.7%) respondents, followed by school of technology with total number of 70 (33.4%) respondents, school of environment studies Gwarzo 20 (9.57%) respondents. Also, school of General studies and School of Rural Development Studies, Rano has total of 20 respondents each representing 9.57% respectively. Table 7.1 shows the distribution of respondents' gender. The table shows that 166 (79.0%) of the respondents are males, while 43(21.0%) of the respondents are females. This implies that more males took part in the research survey than the female's academic staff. This also implies that there are more male academic staff employees than the female's academic staff in Kano State Polytechnics. The age group of the respondents shown in Table 4.4 is between 21 to 30 years old which only 40 (19.3%) respondents. Then 31 to 40 years old with 75 respondents (35.8%), followed by age group 41 to 50 years old with 59 respondents (28.2%). Lastly, age range between 51 years and above with 35 respondents (16.7%).

Table 7.1 shows the distribution of respondents' marital status. The table shows that 157 (75.1%) of the respondents are married, 48(22.9%) of the respondent are single. This implies that majority of the academic staff in Kano State Polytechnic that are participated in this study are married. Table 4.4 above show that the level of education of the respondents which are 92 respondents are BSc and BA and HND level (44.0%), 110(52.6%) respondents are M.Sc. and MA, 7 respondents are PhD (3.4%).

Table 7.2: Procedural Justice Data Description

	Mean	Std. Deviation
I have the opportunity to express my views during the procedures to arrive at my salary	4.09	0.863
I have the influence over my salary level arrived by the procedures	3.85	1.068
My organization apply those procedures to arrive at my salary constantly	4.05	0.867
The procedure to arrive at my salary are free from bias	4.11	0.799
The procedures to arrive at my salary are based on accurate information	4.07	0.938
I have been able to appeal the salary level arrive at by the procedures used by my organization	4.05	0.895
The procedures to arrive at my pay upheld ethical and moral standard	3.88	0.765

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The descriptive statistics for the procedural justice variables are shown in Table 7.2 above. The mean score of the respondents' answers to their perception that "I have the opportunity to express my views during the procedures to arrive at my salary" is 4.09 on a 5-point scale, while the standard deviation is 0.863. This means that sampled the respondents support the fact that the Kano state polytechnic gave him the opportunity to express his views during the procedures to arrive at his salary. For answers, pertaining to "I have the influence over my salary level arrived by the procedures", "my organization apply those procedures to arrive at my salary constantly" and "the procedure to arrive at my salary are free from bias "the means scores for each question items are 3.85, 4.05 and 4.11 respectively. In other words, the respondents agree that "the procedures to arrive at my salary are based on accurate information" mean value of 4.07 and standard deviation of 0.938; "I have been able to appeal the salary level arrive at by the procedures used by my organization" with means score of 4.05 and standard deviation of 0.895. However, they also agree that "the procedures to arrive at my pay upheld ethical and moral standard and outside the polytechnic at mean scores of 3.88.

Table 7.3: Distributive Justice Data Description

	Mean	Std. Deviation
My salary level reflects the effort I have put into my work.	3.37	0.963
My salary level is appropriate for the work I have completed	2.23	0.867
My salary level reflects what I have contributed to the organization	2.97	0.897
My salary level is justified given my performance,	4.05	0.937

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Responses in the table 7.3 above shows that the Kano State polytechnic salary level reflects the effort put into work by its staff, also salary level is appropriate for the work completed at the mean value of 3.37 and 2.73 respectively. The salary level reflects what contributed to the organization at 2.97 values. They agreed that their salary level is justified by their given performance at a value of 4.05.

Table 7.4: Employee Job Satisfaction Data Description

	Mean	Std. Deviation
I am being satisfied with the amount of pay received for the done	2.40	1.233
I am being satisfied with the working condition in my organization	3.73	1.097
I am feeling of getting paid fairly	3.05	1.370
I am being relatively well rewarded financially for the work	3.77	1.078

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The means score of those that emphasize that satisfied with the amount of pay received for the done is 2.40 on 5-point scale, while the standard deviation is 1.233. This means that in the average, respondents do not agree with the amount of pay received for the done. Secondly.

the mean score of those respondents that are of the opinion that they satisfied with the working condition in their organization is 3.73 and standard deviation is 1.097. This implies that in the average, respondents supported the fact that they satisfied with the working condition in their organization. Also, the mean score of "I am feeling of getting paid fairly" is 3.05 while the standard deviation is 1.370. This indicates that in the average on 5-point scale, the respondents agree that they are feeling of getting paid fairly. Furthermore, the mean score for the fourth statement on Table 4.10 above shows 3.77 with the standard deviation of 1.078. Thus, on the average on a 5-point scale, this means that the respondents support the statement.

A critical review of the mean column in Table 4.6 shows that no item has a mean score of less than 2.5 on a 5-point scale. This indicates that respondents agree or strongly agree with all the items questions regarding the procedural justice.

Conclusions

The result of this study shows that job condition impact employee job satisfaction positively. The regression coefficient of the model is positive (0.128), with a p- value of 0.000 significant at only .1%. This indicates a significant positive impact of job condition on employee job satisfaction of academic staff of Kano State Polytechnic. The significant impact of job condition on employee job satisfaction is an indication that good and favorable job condition may necessarily influence the employee job satisfaction. Therefore, the study concluded that job condition has significantly impacted on employee job satisfaction of the academic staff of Kano State Polytechnic.

Recommendation

Undoubtedly, both the government and the regulatory agencies still have a lot to improve in order to increase the quality of job satisfaction in Nigeria. The following recommendations derived from this study may be useful and relevant to the tertiary institution, universities, accounting regulating agencies, government and various other stakeholders.

- i. The present findings suggest that procedural fairness has more effect on their job satisfaction than distributive justice does. Hence, managers should be paying more attention to the means or the process of decision making for the distribution as it will leads to substantial pay-offs in individual job satisfaction.
- ii. This study suggest that managers need to apply rules fairly and consistently to all employees, and rewarding them based on performance and merit without personal bias in order to create a positive perception of distributive justice.
- iii. This study suggested that managers should understand how to reduce employee turnover, increase job satisfaction by making better decisions about the outcomes and procedures for their employees. The research findings indicated the importance to include the management of both fair procedures and fair outcomes. The findings of this study recommend that the management should understand that fair judgments could contribute towards the effective management of workforce through implementation of organizational policies such as reward and performance evaluation policies.
- iv. For the school authority workforce to drive towards employee performance, management of organizations need to enhance organizational support by

implementing organization policies, attitudes, procedures, and decisions that support and value employees' contributions, and cares about their well-being.

- v. The study recommends the policy formulators and implementers to initiate programmes that encourage the staff to enjoy their work, by ensuring that an atmosphere is created, free of harassment and partiality when it comes to the provision of essential services to the staff.
- vi. These findings suggest that there was need for Kano Sate Polytechnic to look into aspect of employee benefit, employee involvement in reward development. The other aspect of remuneration decision should be put in place mechanism that would address this factor to improve job satisfaction The organization also should have essential communication strategy on progress report of rewards policies either by coming up with a policy and given employees written handbooks of reward policies, both monetary and non-monetary satisfaction are as important in job satisfaction. The rewarding system should be in place and the policies to be formulated and implemented.

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